

Investigation of the perception of selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

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Abstract

This study investigated perception of selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design. The target population comprised of 3,584 form two and three students in secondary schools in Nakuru County. A sample of 351 students was drawn using purposive and stratified random sampling. Data was collected through structured self-administered questionnaires. Collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Hypothesis was tested using regression analysis of .05 level of significance. Data was analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer package Version 22.0. The findings of this study may enable coaches to come up with appropriate mechanisms that may help athletes manage their stress effectively. Similarly it may help secondary schools in Kenya institute appropriate interventions to help athletes cope with the stress associated with their sporting careers. The study will also help in building on existing literature related to sources of stress, coping strategies and school based interventions among students athlete in secondary schools. First, the study found out that competition related stress did not influence track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. Second, the study established that institutional related stress negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. Third the study found out that ppersonality related stress positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. Fourth, the study established that stress coping strategies adopted by students' athletes negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. Fifth, the study established that school based interventions used by students' athletes positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education in Conjunction with Department of Sports of the Ministry of Social Services should develop Secondary School Sports Policy with Sports Stress Management Guidelines to help manage the emerging sports related stress in Secondary Schools in Kenya. Copies of the policy should be availed in all Secondary Schools in Kenya for use by both Games Masters and Teacher Counsellors ion the Schools.

Key Words: *Athletics related stress, Stress Management, School Based Interventions, Athletics Track Performance.*

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1.0 Introduction

Stress can come from the environment, or from a person's body or mind (Reece, Brandt and Howie, 2010). Athletes respond to stress differently consisting of three elements: the event or thought (stressor) that triggers stress, the individual perception of it, and the response to it. The physiological response manifest in decreased levels of professional/academic competitive performance and interpersonal problems (Reece, Brandt and Howie, 2010). The competitive sport arena is a highly demanding and potentially stressful environment. In line with this perspective of stress, Fletcher, Hanton and Mellalieu (2006) acknowledge that sport performers must manage a wide range of environmental demands and psychological responses if they are to enhance their athletic performance and sport experience. According to Mellalieu and Hanton (2008) although some performers are able to manage the various causes and consequences of the stress process, many others struggle, resulting in severe impairments to their performance.

In Kenya, Sports are important in educational institutions as it supports academic performance. However, it has been viewed in two different perspectives in schools as far as their contribution to school connectedness is concerned. One perceives sports as having positive effect on student academic performance while others view it as a hindrance to academic success and a waste of students' precious time. Therefore, this duality in the perception of the contribution of sports should be corrected through research findings. Besides, it is important to note that sports can assume other functions other than the traditional function of entertainment and leisure. These functions include; supporting academic objectives, boosting students' self-concept, self-efficacy, affective needs, behavioural needs, social needs, discipline, retention rates among others (Ongonga *et al.*, 2010). Sports are now part of academic curriculum in schools under co-curriculum activities by Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD, 2000).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Kenya is known for its athletic prowess, however, its performance is getting threatened and athletes seem to be resorting to unconventional ways of dealing with their stress related problems. Since athletic talent is mainly identified and discovered in secondary school students, this study set out to examine and provide information on student track athletes' stress level and how it influences performance. Athletes in public secondary schools experience stress like other

elite athletes. The stress is contributed by different factors which if not addressed may affect their track performance. It is not clear which stress factors affect on track performance of public secondary school student athletes, the coping strategies, and school based interventions in place, especially in Nakuru County. This is the research gap that this study was to fill. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence of selected stress factors on track performances of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.0 Literature Review

Sports psychologists and professional athletes have started to evaluate the linkages between emotion and competitive sporting performance, and in particular how moderating and appropriately expressing the experience of emotions can facilitate performance (Stough, Clements, Wallish and Downey, 2009).

Intervention research should be of paramount importance to better understand the most appropriate approach to manage sport performers' stress (Mellalieu and Hanton, 2008) with institutions implementing a number of stress management interventions to optimize different aspects of the transactional stress process in typically one of the following ways: A reduction in stressors, a modification of cognitive appraisals, a reduction in negative affect and an increase in positive effect, or to facilitate effective coping behaviors (Hann, 2000).

The challenge of the extensive participation in athletics includes the increased high expectations by fans and coaches to win at all costs. Hann (2000) found that athletes' participation in competitive sports locally and internationally is linked with competition anxiety and self-centeredness. Winning is certainly a goal of competitive sports, but sometimes players feel more than just the thrill of the game. Being in an environment that stresses winning at all costs can make one totally stressed out (Watson, 2003). This situation overwork athlete to an extent that the start seeing sports as demanding. According to Brush (2002) another major stressor for track athletes is time management. Balancing social life and sport is not an easy task, and can prove to be very stressful. When other stressful events pile on, it leads to burnout.

Sources of stress in sports have been identified and several of them appear to be common in most sports, suggesting that there could be a core group of stressors experienced by all athletes. These common stressors are; pressure to perform at a high standard, concerns about training, institution

and competition environment, individual's personality, coaches' behaviors and coaching styles, and difficulties balancing sport and non-sport commitments (Lombardo, Tan, Jensen and Anderson, 2005). Despite these commonalities, there is support that certain stressors are unique to different sporting environments and populations.

The subject of stress among athletes has been a subject of global studies, for example, Noblet and Gifford (2002) reported stressors that were unique to the Australian footballers they interviewed, included job insecurity from coaches. Puente-Diaz and Anshel (2005) in their study found that the most stress for Mexican tennis players was as a result of receiving negative comments from coaches and relatives, and from opponent cheating. Similar results were found by Anshel and Si (2008) among elite Chinese athletes, who reported making a physical or mental error, after being criticized by the coach and this caused them great stress. Given variations in groups and their environmental demands can give rise to groups of individuals interpreting the same event differently.

Other global studies include Abedalhafiz *et al.* (2010) who carried out an empirical study on sources of stress and coping styles among student-athletes in Jordan universities and found out that with regard to sources of stress, the findings revealed that stress of injury and illness, pressures of competition, conflict with the coach, referee, and spectators were the sources of stress reported by athletes. Although all five variables are capable of producing stress for athletes, stress of injury and illness, which includes being unable to compete as a result of injury or illness, unable to perform at the desired level, and worry about being reinjured during the game, was the most intense source of stress. A possible explanation is that sports are physically demanding and increase potential injury risks.

Hamid and Muhamed (2010) carried out another empirical study on the impact of styles of coping with stress on sport achievement among students of University of Tehran, Iran. The results of their study revealed athletes ignored and/or neglected the problem they were facing. First, instead of conflicting with the source of stress of and wasting some part of mental and physical power for solving the problem through approach coping style, by ignoring and neglecting the matter devotes all his power to the rest of the match and in this way increases his/her chance of success. Second, through avoidant coping style the athlete create a distance between himself/herself and the source of stress and instead of becoming stressed, with more concentration and relief increases the chance of his/her success. Third, through avoidant coping

style the athlete set apart himself/herself from the damaging equation of athlete-the source of stress and by calming the atmosphere of the match uses his/her abilities for a better result and achievement. And finally, in aforementioned situation, the athlete can better use positive and favorable potential facilities, namely, using guidance and opinions of coach, aid and reasonable behavior of referee, and also opponent's disappointment, for victory and success.

In Kenya, Sports are important in educational institutions as it supports academic performance. However, it has been viewed in two different perspectives in schools as far as their contribution to school connectedness is concerned. One perceives sports as having positive effect on student academic performance while others view it as a hindrance to academic success and a waste of students' precious time. Therefore, this duality in the perception of the contribution of sports should be corrected through research findings. Besides, it is important to note that sports can assume other functions other than the traditional function of entertainment and leisure. These functions include; supporting academic objectives, boosting students' self-concept, self-efficacy, affective needs, behavioural needs, social needs, discipline, retention rates among others (Ongonga *et al.*, 2010). Sports are now part of academic curriculum in schools under co-curriculum activities by Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD, 2000). Further, students are encourage to take sports as a career, a fact that exposes students athletes to stress which require them to be taught how to cope with such stress. Ongong'a, (2010) conducted a study on the benefits of sports in secondary schools and the role of sports in secondary education from the perspectives of teachers and students in Kenya. The study revealed that participation in sports is generally beneficial to students in secondary schools by making them physically fit and healthy. However, student athletes like any other elite athletes can suffer from stress, which can affect their track performance. Furthermore, academic performance sometimes is associated with institutional stress which students athletes can suffer from and affect either their track or academic performance and sometimes both. Therefore athletes in public secondary school experience stress contributed by different factors which in turn affect their track performance.

Nakuru County is surrounded by other counties where athletes have emerged. Some of the counties include Likipia which has produced marathon athletes like Sammy Wanjiru, Alice Aprot, Julius Kariuki among others. Because of the proximity with neighbouring counties, Nakuru County also nurture athletes at secondary school level.

2.2 Knowledge Gap

The researcher carried out review of various literatures related to; concept of stress among athletes, athletes' performance in relation to institutional stress and athletes' performance. The critically review showed that there is still need of research to be done on perception of selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The theoretical aspect of this study is informed by Cognitive Activation Theory of stress (CATS) by Lazarus & Folkman (1984). This theoretical perspective defines stress as a relationship between individuals and their environments. First, stress and coping are viewed as manifestations of dynamic and evaluative interplays between individuals and their environments. Secondly, the cognitive theory of stress and coping suggests that stress and coping are bidirectional processes in that individuals are both agents and objects of environmental change. The theory relies on an assumption that individuals engage in a cognitive appraisal of the environmental condition leading to an evaluation of perceived threats. The cognitive processes include coping mechanisms, an attempt to moderate the environment or an internal attempt to regulate the emotional distress caused by the stressor.

The theory further suggests that repeated experiences with a stimulus allow individuals to adapt and regulate themselves (Ursin & Eriksen, 2004). According to the theory experience may produce discomfort for the individual, arousal and stress is vital to the operation of complex brains. The purpose of arousal is to compel the individual to remove the source of the stress "alarm" and the alarm itself, similar to how it has been argued that the function of effect is to direct action (Frijda, 1996). Or, if not removed, the individual then is able to sustain the activation necessary to handle the stressor. Consequently, the stress experience is part of an adaptive and beneficial system that has survived the test of evolution. CATS theory argues that because the stress alarm occurs when there is a discrepancy between what is desired and what is reality, individuals will associate a probability with the likelihood of abolishing the alarm and its source (Ursin, 2005). This expectancy has a strong influence on the level of arousal. At its simplest, if the person has control and expects a desired outcome, then the alarm may not be

activated (i.e., stressors may not be felt, psychologically or physiologically). However, if the future is unpredictable and/or an individual does not have the necessary resources to handle the demands, then the alarm is activated. Further, there are instances when individuals do not possess the necessary resources to handle the situation and dissociating themselves from it thus engaging a passive response that provokes a positive outcome expectation, reducing stress activation.

To account for individual differences in the activation of the stress response, Lazarus (1966) identified six key decisional components within appraisal and the development of stress, three primary components and three secondary components. Primary appraisal of an event involves addressing what is happening and whether the event is worthy of one's attention (Lazarus, 1993). The individual determines whether the potential stressor is a threat based on previous experiences, knowledge about oneself, and knowledge about the event. Primary appraisal includes three components that are related to the motivational aspects of the encounter with the event. Specifically, primary appraisal includes addressing goal relevance, goal congruence, and the type of ego involvement. Goal relevance indicates whether there is anything at stake to be interfered with by the perceived threat or barrier. If there is nothing to be lost by the presentation of the threat, then no stress response will occur. If the situation is viewed as relevant to the individual's achievement goals, a stress response will result.

The study will also be informed by Rational-Emotive-Behaviour-Theory (REBT) is one of the cognitive behavioural approaches which was founded in 1955 by an American clinical psychologist, Albert Ellis (Scott, 1995). He was the first to pinpoint that people suffer from stress and other conflicts because they believe things which are false. Ellis maintained that emotional and behavioural disturbance was primarily caused by rigid and absolutistic beliefs in the form of musts, shoulds, have to's, got to's (Melgosa, 2000) - demands we make on ourselves, others, the world. In other words, it is individuals who largely upset themselves rather than events, circumstances or other people. In order to minimize emotional disturbance and produce more goal orientated behaviour, rigid or irrational beliefs are pinpointed, challenged and changed to a rational belief system, according to Ellis, 1972.

The stress management strategies would mainly be devoted to cathartic techniques, relaxation, exercise, healthy eating, positive thinking and 'cooling off periods. These are the suggested strategies towards managing stress in my literature review section. From the REBT perspective, these are essentially short term and palliative methods; unless demandingness is disputed and changed to rational ideas through teaching individuals the ABC model, it is unlikely that stress levels will fall.

When examining the experience of chronic stress for athletes, individual differences become apparent. Stress values mostly fall on the moderate side, yet athletes are significantly more stressed on average than people from the general population; whereas athletes with alarmingly high indicators of stress are mainly elite student athletes (shortly EA) who pursue a school or university career in addition to their elite-level sport (Richartz & Sallen, 2017). Chronic stress seems to play an important role in the dropout of athletic careers (Baron-Thiene & Alfermann, 2015). Exhaustion, depression, and burnout are some of the symptoms often mentioned in connection with chronic stress (Gustafsson, Madigan, & Lundkvist, 2017).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Influence of Stress Factors on Athletes' Performances among Secondary School Students in Nakuru County, Kenya

Figure 1 indicates the relationship between independent, moderating and dependent variables. The independent variables which include competition stress, institutional stress, personality stress, personality type, coping strategies and school based interventions are thought to have an influence on the dependent variable which is Athletes' Performances among Secondary School Students in Nakuru County, Kenya. Affecting this process is the moderating variable which includes background factors like religion, and state of health of athletes, cultures where students' athletes come from, quality of counseling in the schools and motivation by Games Teachers. These factors can moderate the relationship between independent variables and dependent variable. The model as conceptualized in this study emphasizes on how the independent

variables may influence the dependent variables. The study hypothesizes that unmanaged competing stressors, school based stressors are not managed well based on the student athlete personality, it affect their coping ability. Depending on other factors as the student athlete background, culture, quality of counseling and motivation by Games Teacher, all these factors in combination would influence their tack performance.

3.0 Research Design

This study undertook an exploratory survey approach with ex-post facto design. *Ex post facto* research, by its very design, investigates the world as it naturally occurs and explores phenomena that have already occurred (Johnson & Christensen, 2008). The study targeted 3,584 form two and three students in schools with high performance in athletics.

Given the sample size of 351 as per Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sampling table, the following formula was used to calculate stratified sample;

$$ss = \frac{zp}{tp} Xs$$

Where ss – stratified sample, zp –zonal population, tp – target population and s – sample. The sample size distribution for the study is shown in Table 2. The study purposively picked 5 athlete coaches and 5 Teacher Counselors as key informants to give deeper insight into selected stress factors influencing track performance of Student Athletes. The researcher took half of the sample size to represent both the gender in order to analyze how the different gender responds to stress.

Table 1: Sample Size of Student Athletes in School in Nakuru County

Zone	No. Schools	Total No. of Form		Male	Female
		2 and 3 Students	Sample Size	Athletes	Athletes
A	4	430	42	21	21
B	6	620	61	30	30
C	3	664	65	33	32
D	4	820	80	40	40
E	7	1050	103	52	51
Total	24	3584	351	176	175

The study used a structured questionnaire to collect primary data. Descriptive (frequencies and percentages) analysis and inferential statistics such as chi-square test and Pearson's correlation analyses were used to analyze data after appropriate data coding. Descriptive statistics were used to investigate or explore one variable at a time. To test the hypotheses, chi-square test and Pearson's correlation analyses were conducted for each hypothesis and the results interpreted leading to the rejection or acceptance of the null hypotheses stated earlier. All hypotheses was tested at $\alpha=.05$.

4.0 Findings and Discussions

4.1 Multivariate regression analysis

This section presents the results of multivariate regression analysis of perception of selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The researcher combined each of the sub-variables under each of the five stress factors influencing track performance; competition related factors, instructional related stresses, personality related stress, stress coping strategies and school based interventions. The dependent variable is students athletes track performance.

Table 2: R Square Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.396 ^a	.157	.144	.58813

Results from Table 35 revealed that the R value was 0.396 whereas R Square was 0.157, which indicated an average degree of correlation. The R^2 value indicates how much of the dependent variable, "students' athletes track performance", was explained by the independent variables, "competition related stress, institutional related stress, personality related stress, stress coping strategy and school based intervention". In this case, 15.7% was the R Squared, which was average indicating an average degree of correlation.

Table 3: ANOVA Results

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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1	Regression	21.447	5	4.289	12.401	.000 ^b
	Residual	115.529	334	.346		
	Total	136.975	339			

The Predictors: "competition related stress, institutional related stress, personality related stress, stress coping strategy and school based intervention". The Dependable variable: "students' athletes track performance". Table 36 indicated that the regression model predicted the outcome variable significantly with $p=0.000$, which was less than 0.05, and indicated that although the R Square was not large; overall, the model statistically and significantly predicted the outcome variable.

Table 4: Multivariate Marketing Stress Related Factors and Performance on the Track

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	1.531	.281			5.447	.000
Competition	.004	.003	.070		1.223	.222
personality	.017	.004	.245		4.376	.000
Institutional factors	.011	.006	.107		1.965	.050
Coping strategies	-.018	.007	-.182		-2.794	.006
School interventions	.021	.006	.201		3.450	.001

When competition related stress, institutional related stress, personality related stress, stress coping strategy and school based intervention were combined in multivariate regression, the study established an insignificant influence of competition related stress with students athletes on track performance $r = 0.004$, $p = 0.222 > 0.05$. Further findings indicated that personality related stress significantly influenced students athletes on track performance $r = 0.017$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. Institutional stress factor had significant influence on students' athletes on track performance $r = 0.011$, $p = 0.05$. Findings on coping strategies established that stress coping strategies had influence on students' athletes on track performance $r = -0.018$, $p = 0.006$ and that school based intervention also had influence on students athletes on track performance $r = 0.021$, $p = 0.001$.

The general objective of the study was to assess the perception of selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County,

Kenya. The study established that selected stress factors influenced the sales track performance of student athletes. This was because apart from competition related factors, institutional related stress, personality related stress, stress coping strategy and school based intervention influenced track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. As indicated in Table 23, from the unstandardized coefficients, the following equation was developed: $y = 1.513 + 0.004x_1 + 0.017x_2 + 0.011x_3 - 0.018x_4 + 0.021 + \varepsilon$

4.2 The moderating factors on selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

The study also analyzed the moderating effect of stress factors on students' athletes on track performance. The moderating independent variables analyzed included; student athletes background, state of health, cultural background, quality of counseling and motivation by games teacher.

Table 5: Moderating Stress Related Factors and Performance on the Track

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	1.531	.281			5.447	.000
Competition	.004	.003	.070		1.223	.222
Personality	.017	.004	.245		4.376	.000
Institutional	.011	.006	.107		1.965	.050
Coping strategies	-.018	.007	-.182		-2.794	.006
School interventions	.021	.006	.201		3.450	.001
2 (Constant)	1.523	.284			5.367	.000
Competition	.004	.003	.072		1.239	.216
Personality	.018	.004	.249		4.241	.000
Institutional	.011	.006	.108		1.967	.050
Coping strategies	-.018	.007	-.176		-2.487	.013
School interventions	.021	.006	.203		3.440	.001
Moderating	-.011	.050	-.014		-.214	.831

Table 5 shows the findings before and after interaction of moderating stress factors was introduced as moderating variable. The study established insignificant relationship between competition stress factors and students athlete track performance $r = 0.004$, $p = 0.222 > 0.05$ before the interaction of moderating variable and $r = 0.004$, $p = 0.216 > 0.05$ after the interaction of the moderating variable. Further findings indicate a significant influence of personality related stress and students athlete track performance $r = 0.017$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ before interaction of the moderating variables and significant influence $r = 0.018$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ after interaction of the moderating variables.

The study also established significant influence of institutional related factors and students athlete track performance $r = 0.011$, $p = 0.05$ before introduction of moderating factors and similar significant influence values after the interaction of the moderating factors. The study also established significant influence of stress coping strategies and students athlete track performance $r = -0.018$, $p = 0.006 < 0.05$ before the introduction of interaction of moderating variables and similar significance influence. Finally, the study established significant influence of school based interventions and students athlete track performance $r = 0.021$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$ before the introduction of interaction of moderating variables and similar significance influence. The moderating factors on their own had insignificant influence on students athlete track performance $r = -0.011$, $p = 0.831 > 0.05$.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.3. Conclusions

The main purpose of the study was to investigate perception of selected stress factors influencing track performance of student athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made: the first specific objective of the study was to find out whether competition related stress influences students' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study found out that competition related stress did not influence track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The second specific objective of the study was to examine influence of institutional related stress on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru

County, Kenya. The study established that institutional related stress negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

The third specific objective of the study was to find out the influence of personality related stress on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study found out that personality related stress positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The fourth specific objective was to analyse whether stress coping strategies adopted by students' athletes has any influence on track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study established that stress coping strategies adopted by students' athletes negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The fifth objective of the study was to examine whether school based interventions used by students' athletes has any influence on track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study established that school based interventions used by students' athletes positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

5.2 Recommendations

In view of the findings and the conclusions of this study the following recommendations are made; the Ministry of Education in Conjunction with Department of Sports of the Ministry of Social Services should develop Secondary School Sports Policy with Sports Stress Management Guidelines to help manage the emerging sports related stress in Secondary Schools in Kenya. Copies of the policy should be availed in all Secondary Schools in Kenya for use by both Games Masters and Teacher Counsellors ion the Schools.

Secondary schools in Kenya should put in place strategies for boosting positive competition related stress as a means to boosting track performance among student athletes. Secondly the professionals involved in management of sports and games as well as guidance and counselling departments in secondary schools in Kenya should come up with adequate programmes and ways of managing institutional related stress to mitigate against the negative influences it has on track performance among student athletes. Third, there should be proper arrangements for boosting positive personality related stress to strengthen the observed positive influence on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. Four, Guidance and Counselling Departments in secondary schools in Kenya should design appropriate programmes

for proper stress coping strategies adopted by students' athletes to reduce the negative influence on track performance among athletes. Guidance and Counselling Departments should design appropriate programmes for school based interventions used by students' athletes to increase the positive influence on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

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